

COMMON MISTAKES THAT STUDENTS MAKE IN THEIR SPEAKING

Umarova Sevinch Allayor qizi

Student of Samarkand State Institut of Foreign language

Gmail: usevinch766@gmail.com

Scientific supervisor: **Zubaydova Nilufar Nematullayevna**

Senior teacher (PhD) Samarkand State Institut of Foreign language

Annotation: In this article English language learner's mistakes and problems related to their speaking skills are analyzed. The article demonstrates the main difficulties which arise during language learning, types of mistakes in speaking and how to avoid them. Aspects that should be paid attention to the development of speech of students are described. Also, the importance of clearly expressing one's thoughts and participating in dialogue is emphasized.

Keyword: english, speaking, learning, mistakes, speech, communication, skills, language learning, communicative difficulties, selfassessment, expression, students, effective teaching methods, teachers.

English has become the language of global communication in these days. Therefore, improving speaking skills in the process of learning language is important. Many students tend to make some mistakes in their speaking activities and so these mistakes can have a negative effect on their communication. One of the most essential aspects in language learning process is having ability to express one's thoughts clearly and fluently. This article determines the most common mistakes of English language learners in their speaking skills and how to eliminate them.

There are several reasons why English language learners have difficulty with speaking skills. First of all, many students don't feel comfortable themselves in their speech when they use new or complex words and grammatical structures. In this kind of situations, errors related to incorrect pronunciation, word order and grammatical mistakes may appear.

Firstly, students often do not know how to pronounce new words and this leads to misunderstandings in their communication. As a result, they face so many mistakes in pronunciation. For example, some new words and phrases in English may sound similar in Uzbek, but have different meanings and usage. In order to reduce speech errors, teachers need to use special exercises and audio materials, then it helps to improve pronunciation.

Secondly, grammatical errors also play an important role in speaking. Most of the time students use verbs that do not match tense or person. For instance,

incorrect sentences like "I go to the market yesterday" can cause mutual misunderstanding. For this reason, having perfect knowledge of grammar when expressing their thoughts is necessary for students. So to help them their teachers should organize more practical exercises and games.

Additionally, during language learning some mistakes in communication may occur. Language learners often make mistakes in expressing themselves because they feel uncomfortable when being judged by others. In such a situation, students cannot express their thoughts freely, so this affects their results negatively. Thus, teachers should organize the communication environment in a comfortable and supportive way. In addition to this, English learners often lose confidence, as a result, it causes mistakes in the communication process. Students tend to underestimate themselves, which further reduces their speaking skills. Teachers need to help them to build confidence by encouraging, motivating them and evaluating their progress.

To eliminate errors, students should develop themselves through self-assessment. Analyzing one's own speech, identifying strengths and weaknesses can help to improve their speaking skill. And also, students can record their speech and analyze it later. This method is effective in self-evaluation and reducing their mistakes in the future.

In conclusion, there are many ways to overcome mistakes in English language learner's speaking skills. Analyzing mistakes in speaking is also essential in the process of learning English. Students often make mistakes which related to their pronunciation, grammar and communication that negatively affects their participation in speaking activities. As this article points out, errors in pronunciation can lead to misunderstandings in communication, so it is necessary for students to focus on learning accurate and correct pronunciation.

In addition, by increasing their self-confidence and creating safe environment students can develop their speaking skills easily. The process of self-assessment and free expression allow students to identify and correct errors. Teachers need to help students to improve their speaking skills through effective teaching methods and support. Thus, it is essential to pay attention to many aspects in order to eliminate mistakes in the process of learning English.

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